

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women Entrepreneurs in Sindh, Pakistan

Annam Inayat

Lecturer, Department of Management Sciences, NUML Hyderabad Campus, Pakistan.

Dodo Khan Alias Khalid Malokani

Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration Government College University, Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Duaa Ayaz

Student at HIAST, Hyderabad, Pakistan.

Received on: 06-01-2022

Accepted on: 09-02-2022

Abstract

Women Entrepreneurship in Pakistan; Motivations, Success and Barriers a study on Sindh, Pakistan. An entrepreneur is someone who explores new opportunities, business, products/ services, or ideas (Kuratko 2016). During the early 1980s, the Women Entrepreneurship has elicited suitable recognition, especially as a driver of economic growth and development. According to Roomi and Parrott (2008), the women position throughout Pakistan is not homogenous. Cultural practices and norms related to role and status of women and religious prescriptions vary widely in the Pakistani society. Pakistani researchers have also critically examined existing literature on women entrepreneurship in Pakistan. Primary focus of this research study is about the very less work or no research evidence found in the province of Sindh, Pakistan on women entrepreneurship (Ashique, Najia, Ali, and Rajjar, 2012; Saad and Rajjar 2015). The data in this study is Primary, and involve gathering of research figures straight from the respondents using a structured 5-point Likert scale with the help of questionnaire based on women entrepreneurship. The population of the study consist of female entrepreneurs running businesses or involved in entrepreneurial activities from both urban and rural areas of Sindh. In this study, to ensure an adequate sample, data is collected from 150 respondents (female entrepreneurs). Regression method was used to analyze the data. This analysis is performed with the help of SPSS software. The current study uses the dependence model for testing the data because each hypothesis measures the impact of one independent variable on three dependent variables that is motivation, success and barriers women entrepreneurs face while becoming entrepreneurs. Result of this study suggests that 71% of the female are of age group 15-25 years, are energetic and most willing to start their own business, among all motivational factors including to be their own boss is having strongly positive impact to peruse entrepreneurship

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

rather than regular job, among all success factors female entrepreneurs believed that having good managerial skills lead to successful business. Weak economy and lack of laws regulations in the country is causing a huge barrier to begin their own business according to the responses of entrepreneurs belonging to female group. Furthermore, the study suggests that Government of Pakistan should propose business laws and ensure its practice in the small and medium size enterprises. Also, there are many programs offered by the Pakistani Government to promote entrepreneurship but female and nascent entrepreneurs are not aware of these programs at large. So, these programs should be introduced in all educational institutes and universities so that female entrepreneurs should get most of it.

Key words: Women entrepreneurs, Internal and external factors, Motivation, Success and Barriers.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

During the early 1980s', the Women Entrepreneurship has elicited suitable recognition, especially as a driver of economic growth and development. The global economy, since the early 1970s has undergone significant and irreversible changes. Various economic, social and political transformations contributed towards a more volatile business climate emergence, in order to survive, small and micro businesses have to compete effectively. In these circumstances, new opportunities are created for female gender entrepreneurs to establish their personal businesses. The prospect of forming a business or a firm is significant and an attractive alternative, since women have to balance their family responsibilities along with the professional work. Therefore, the concept of entrepreneurship is more beneficial and attractive for women, as compared to full-time paid employment in this respect. It has been witnessed that there is a substantial growth in the number businesses owned controlled and owned to women entrepreneurs all over the world, which substantially contributes especially towards the growth and development of the developing nations (Leszczyński, 2013).

Pakistan is a developing country, which is regarded as having one of the best advanced microfinance settings in the world. While, the outreach to female cadre entrepreneurs and borrowers, at the same time, is the lowest one on global level. For the economic growth and inclusion agenda of Pakistan, fostering women entrepreneurship is significant. In addition, for starting and growing a business, access to financial services for the businesses is an important component (Haq and Safavian, 2013). According to Roomi and Parrott (2008), due to interconnection of gender with other exclusion forms in the society, the women status in Pakistan is not homogenous. Cultural practices and norms related to role and status of women and religious prescriptions vary widely in the Pakistani society. Moreover, social, capitalist and feudal traditions can restrict operations related to female cadre entrepreneurs, during their whole working lives. In comparing a man's situation with a women's one finds systematic subordination, which is determined and controlled by the forces of patriarchy. Throughout Pakistan, the women occupational opportunities' availability is greatly restricted by these practices.

Women entrepreneurship in Pakistan is yet a relatively new concept due to low women economic development. Despite of donors' efforts and governmental commitment to reduce

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

gender inequalities, a significant amount of effort is required to uplift women socio-economic status by developing and implementing action plan in regard of economic activities for the women in Pakistan.

The current research study is based on Women entrepreneurship in the province of Sindh, Pakistan. The research study tries to explore the motivations, obstacles, and performance of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. It inspects the influence of internal and external factors on the elements that determine the women entrepreneurs' activities (motivations, performance, barriers). The internal factors consist of age, marital status, children and family support, whereas the external factors are business expansion and financial capabilities of women entrepreneurs.

1.2. Problem Statement

Women entrepreneurship is regarded as an important tool for facilitating female empowerment. It is significantly important for an economy to enable women getting the same opportunities as men. However, to promote, encourage, and support women entrepreneurship, there is need to determine the factors affecting its different aspects. Previously, the research studies have paid heed on the concepts and the factors influencing women entrepreneurship (Alam, Jani & Omar, 2011; Zhouqiaoqin, Ying, Lu & Kumah, 2013; Makweba, 2014). The extant literature has widely acknowledged the influence of internal factors including family support and personal characteristics (Welsh, Memili & Kaciak, 2016; Bhardwaj, 2014; Vадnjаl & Vадnjаl, 2013), and the external variables, such as firm expansion and financing patterns/needs (Niethammer, Saeed, Mohamed & Charafi, 2007; Constantinidis, Cornet & Asandei, 2006). The research studies on the subject have also explored the aspects related to motivations, barriers, and success of women entrepreneurship (Akehurs, Simarro & Mas-Tur, 2012; Leszczyński, 2013; Le and Raven, 2015). However, with respect to women entrepreneurship context in Pakistan, a research gap in the literature exists, especially in relation to women entrepreneurs' motivations, success and barriers. Therefore, the current research study examines the impact of the different internal and external factors on motivation, success and barriers that determine the women entrepreneurs' activity in Pakistan.

1.3. Research Objectives

I. To evaluate the impact of the internal factors (entrepreneur's age, family support, marital status and Children at start-up) on the motivation, success and barriers that determine the women entrepreneurs' activity in Sindh Pakistan.

II. To evaluate the impact of the external factors (firm expansion and financial capabilities) on the motivation, success and barriers that determine the women entrepreneurs' activities in Sindh Pakistan.

1.4. Research Questions

Following are the research questions of the study:

1. What is the influence of different internal factors (entrepreneur's age, family support, marital status and Children at start-up) on the motivations, success and barriers of Women entrepreneurs in Sindh, Pakistan?

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

2. What is the impact of external factors (firm expansion and financial capabilities) on the motivation, success and barriers of Women entrepreneurs Sindh, Pakistan?

1.5. Limitations

This study has its few limitations firstly, this study just emphasis on the experience by females running their own business. So further researches can investigate different elements of entrepreneurial behaviour like intentions and motives for the identification of opportunity or self-employment. Secondly, this study was conducted in province of Sindh only, further studies might focus on the other Provinces of Pakistan for generalizing the results. Also, this research only focuses on female, so in an attempt to describe whether motives or barriers for starting business differ on the gender basis in the same country, further research can explore the entrepreneurial experience of male entrepreneurs.

2.1. Literature Review

The following detail provide the key findings of the literature review:

Women Entrepreneurship in Pakistan

Makhijani, Kumbhar, Mughal and Talpur (2015), the study finds that lack of family cooperation is the most common social problem among the rural women entrepreneurs, followed by lack of reorganization of work of the women. Among the financial problems, the study finds complex loaning procedure and lack of credit facilities as the main financial problem. According to the findings, the motivation of women entrepreneurs is affected by self-satisfaction, personal ambition, contribution to family income and earning money for personal use. Moreover, the perceived barriers include, customs and local culture, capital unavailability, lack of guidance, and inadequate education (Mahmood, Khalid, Sohail and Babak, 2012).

According to Roomi and Parrott (2008), the female entrepreneurs' economic potential is not being realized due to lack of training and agency assistance, information technology, business premises, land and access to capital. The Essential attitudes of a male dominant society, also create formidable challenges for female cadre entrepreneurs in Pakistan, in addition to small encouragement from the family of female entrepreneurs, resulting in dearth of social capital and limited spatial mobility. Roomi and Harrison (2010), the study shows that women-only training can be used to alleviate the women entrepreneurship barriers in capital of the training participants. The study finds that the major constraints relate to the Family, Self and Social Domain, perused by Financial & Economic domain, Political & Environmental Domain and later on by Marketing & Mobility (Anjum, Khan, Raza and Fatima, 2012).

Financing and Expansion in Women Entrepreneurship

According to Ekpe, Mat and Razak (2010), the microfinance factors including credit (use of loan and loan size) and savings have a substantial encouraging influence on women entrepreneurial activities or performance. In another study Carter et al., (2003), found that outside equity and financing odds are significantly influenced by graduate education only. In regard of social capital influences, Pakistan that allows development of competencies and the use of bootstrapping and no impact on the likelihood of using equity funding. The study also finds the network diversity is in positive direction, while professional advisory relationship

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

is negatively associated with personal financing sources. The results of the study proved that for so many women entrepreneurs, there are specific barriers and financing patterns. The financing patterns are influenced by women entrepreneurs' categories related to social, human and financial capital variables (Constantinidis, Cornet and Asandei, 2006).

Niethammer, Saeed, Mohamed and Charafi (2007), explained that Women's reach to finance is important for the elimination of social gender bias, improvement of social well-being, poverty alleviation, and the generation of female employment. It also increases women's economic activity in Pakistan.

Family Support and Personal Characteristics

According to Welsh, Memili and Kaciak (2016), Family support may increase personal problems of Turkish women entrepreneurs due to legitimacy, authority and business interference of the family members. Family backup, on the other hand, helps women entrepreneurs to identify usefulness of prior work experiences and managerial skill deficiencies. According to the findings, appropriate education and professional training serve as a source of innovative ideas, which improves productivity of the entrepreneurship. The findings revealed significant association between education and making available entrepreneurial platform to the female cadre for initiating their enterprise venture (Bhardwaj, 2014).

According to the results, the support of husbands in the women entrepreneurial activity is very important, especially in the form of emotional support (empowerment and belief). Moreover, financial support in this respect is also highly appreciated (Vadnjaj and Vadnjaj, 2013). According to Orser, Riding and Manley (2006), the study found that except for external equity capital, there is no difference between women and men entrepreneurs to seek all external financing types. The study also finds that it is equally likely that male and female entrepreneurs obtain capital when applying for financing. The findings reveal that, for business support, help and advice, a woman entrepreneur looks towards her husband (Kirkwood, 2009).

Motivations, Barriers, and Success Factors

Akehurs, Simarro and Mas-Tur (2012), found that the internal factors like (age, family, marital status and children) and the external factors like (financing and expansion) are significantly affecting the performance, motivation, and barriers to success of the firms created by women. The study revealed that the broad category of women entrepreneurs' success consists of managerial skills, psychological characteristics, demographic descriptor, contextual and environmental factors (Leszczyński, 2013). Hughes (2006), sorted out that freedom, independence, and Work-Family balance as the most significant factors among women entrepreneurs regarding the starting of own business. Values and perceptions of entrepreneurship influence women entrepreneurs' perceived success. Similarly, the variables influence the motivations of women business owners (Le and Raven, 2015).

Tlaiss (2013), analysed that Emirati women entrepreneurial motivations are reflective of special features of traditional, wealthy, and Muslim GCC and UAE contexts. The women entrepreneurs are also inspired by need for freedom, independence, and autonomy. A number of factors influence women to take up business ventures, which include personal

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

development, economic rewards, prestige, advancement, achievement, and ability of utilization (Kaur and Bawa,1999). According to Roy and Manna (2014), the research study finds that helping husband and family, and self-motivation are the most important motivational factors for the women entrepreneurs.

The study highlights that shortage of education and training is a barrier to women entrepreneurship, and training programs can help in resolving these problems (Idrus, Pauzi and Munir, 2014). Ekpe, Mat and Razak (2010), found that Barriers to women entrepreneurship include societal discrimination, low household income, unemployment and poverty.

Lockyer and George (2012), explored that accessibility to training; financial risk; and dependence on friends or family to setup a business are the major barriers in female entrepreneurship development.

In another research study Sadi and Al-Ghazali (2010), explained that barriers in women entrepreneurship in Saudi Arabia include oligopolistic attitude of investors, society restrictions, lack of support from the community, lack of coordination among departments of government, lack of governmental support, and lack of market studies.

According to another research finding, the most prominent women entrepreneurship barriers include industrial support, access to technology, knowledge to collaborate, financial assistance, pressure to achieve, time for training, evidences on opportunities, training opportunities, and interaction with males (Al-Sadi, Belwal and Al-Badi, 2011).

Noorinasab and Azmoon (2014), assessed that the main barriers in women entrepreneurship include family issues, education, training, financing, physical resources, marketing, socio-cultural factors, patriarchal Society, and rules and regulations. According to Jamali (2009), the finding of the paper revealed the

significance of all micro, meso and macro level factors and integration of multiple lens and units of analysis to access the complication of experiences of women entrepreneurs in specific context. Furthermore, Alam, Jani and Omar (2011), sorted out that internal motivation, ties based on social, and family support, influence success of WEs significantly and positively Zhouqiaoqin, Ying, Lu and Kumah (2013), found success of women entrepreneurship is significantly influenced by women characteristics, human capital, family support and entrepreneurial motivations. Contrary to this, Makweba (2014), indicated a number of factors influenced the success, which include personal financial discipline, personal commitment, individual family background, owner initiative, friendly working environment, experience and capital base.

The research study finds that individual characteristics of women, business strategies and business management, parental influence, networking, motives and goals, and entrepreneurial orientation put its impact on the task performance of women entrepreneurs in Malaysia (Ming-Yen and Siong-Choy, 2007). Dangi (2014), concluded that growth of women entrepreneurs and MSMEs is contributing to the growth of Indian economy.

Research Methodology

3.1. Research Approach

The findings of the study aim to explore women entrepreneurship in Pakistan, with a concentration on motivations, obstacles, and success of women entrepreneurs. For this

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

purpose, the study adopted a 'Quantitative research approach' to examine the impact of internal and external factors on the motivations, obstacles, and success of women entrepreneurs.

3.2. Research Purpose

In this study, the association between the given variables related to women entrepreneurship are already defined, therefore it follows an 'explanatory research purpose' to further explain the problem in the context of Pakistan.

3.3. Research Design

The research study involves correlational design to examine the relationship between different influential factors/variables in women entrepreneurship and motivations, success and barriers. In a correlational design, the variables are measured and the association between them is defined (Bordens, 2006).

3.4. Data Source

The data is collected directly from the participants using a structured questionnaire based on women entrepreneurship.

3.5. Population of the Study

Population of the study consists of women entrepreneurs from Sindh, Pakistan, operating in different small and medium size business SMEs.

3.6. Sampling Strategy

In primary research, sampling is a key component; in this case, the 'convenience sampling' technique is used. In primary research, sampling is a key component; in this case, the 'convenience sampling' technique is utilised, which is a type of non-probability sampling that considers respondents' accessibility and closeness. is utilised, which is a type of non-probability sampling that considers respondents' accessibility and closeness. (Weiss & Weiss, 2012).

3.7. Sample Size

To ensure an adequate sample, data is collected from 150 respondents (female entrepreneurs).

3.8. Research Instrument

The data source used for this study is primary, and is collected through direct means from the research participants with the help of a multiple items 5-point Likert scale Questionnaire. It means that the research instrument of the study is the questionnaire measuring various internal and external factors, along with women entrepreneurs' motivation, success and barriers.

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

3.9. Research Hypotheses

Based on the objectives of the current research study, proposed hypotheses are given below:

- H1: The impact of firm expansion on the motivation, success and barriers of women entrepreneurs is significant.
- H2: The impact of financial capabilities on the motivation, success and barriers of women entrepreneurs is significant.
- H3: The age of women entrepreneurs significantly influences their motivation, success and barriers.
- H4: The marital status of women entrepreneurs significantly influences their motivation, success and barriers.
- H5: The number of children at business start-up affects women entrepreneurs' motivation, success and barriers.
- H6: The family support affects women entrepreneurs' motivation, success and barriers, which characterize the activity of the business.

Figure 3.1. Conceptual Model

The above research model is derived from Akehurs, Simarro and Mas-Tur (2012). According to the model, the study proposed to examine the impact of various external and internal factors on women entrepreneurs' motivation, success and barriers.

Empirical Results

Empirical research is based on the first-hand observation and measurement of phenomena by the researcher. The data acquired in this manner can be compared to a theory or hypothesis, but the results are still based on real-world experience.

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The process of converting raw data into a form that is easy to understand and analyse, i.e., rearranging, ordering, and altering data to provide meaningful information about the presented data. Descriptive analysis is a sort of data analysis that helps to explain, show, or summarise data points in a constructive way so that patterns can develop that satisfy all of the data's conditions.

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

Descriptive statistics

Table 1: Age distribution of the respondent

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 15 to 25	22	71.0	71.0	71.0
26 to 35	3	9.7	9.7	80.6
36 to 45	3	9.7	9.7	90.3
46 to 55	3	9.7	9.7	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

The results from the first question clearly show that a huge number of respondents belong to the middle-aged group that is 15-25 years 71.0 % of people are between 15-25years. A small amount of 9.7% was the employees aged above 56 have also participated in answering the questionnaire for the survey.

SECTION 01: MOTIVATION

Table 02: To be own boss

TO BE OWN_BOSS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	10	32.3	32.3	32.3
Agree	12	38.7	38.7	71.0
Neutral	7	22.6	22.6	93.5
Disagree	1	3.2	3.2	96.8
Strongly Disagree	1	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 02 shows that most of the women chooses Agree and Strongly Agree that shows women want to be their own boss and willing to have their own business and want to be entrepreneurs.

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

Table03: To Gain Public Recognition

GAIN_RECOGNITION

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	8	25.8	25.8	25.8
Agree	12	38.7	38.7	64.5
Neutral	10	32.3	32.3	96.8
Disagree	1	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 03 shows that the most of the women participates chooses between Agree and Strongly Agree that shows the interest of women in public recognition. Majority of women want to gain public recognition.

Table 04: I will always have job security Table 04 shows that the majority chooses Agree to have job security which means women Think that having own business is always have job security.

Table 04: To be having job security

JOB_SECURITY

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	8	25.8	25.8	25.8
Agree	15	48.4	48.4	74.2
Neutral	3	9.7	9.7	83.9
Disagree	1	3.2	3.2	87.1
Strongly Disagree	4	12.9	12.9	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

Table 05: To increase my income level

INCREASE_INCOME

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	12	38.7	38.7	38.7
	Agree	13	41.9	41.9	80.6
	Neutral	5	16.1	16.1	96.8
	Disagree	1	3.2	3.2	100.0
	Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 05: shows that majority of women selected between Agree and Strongly Agree that shows women, who are entrepreneurs are in the want of increasing their income and grow more which will take them to the better ness of themselves as well as for the society.

SECTION 02: BARRIERS

Table 01: Weak economy

WEAK_ECONOMY

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	8	25.8	25.8	25.8
Agree	11	35.5	35.5	61.3
Neutral	7	22.6	22.6	83.9
Disagree	3	9.7	9.7	93.5
Strongly Disagree	2	6.5	6.5	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 01 of section 02 shows that majority selectees agree that shows they are agreed with weak economy of Pakistan which impacts bad on their business and they don't have much opportunities to expand their business in Pakistan specially.

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

TABLE 02: LACK OF MARKETING TRAINING
LACK OF MANAGEMENT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	7	22.6	22.6	22.6
Agree	8	25.8	25.8	48.4
Neutral	9	29.0	29.0	77.4
Disagree	6	19.4	19.4	96.8
Strongly Disagree	1	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 02 of section 02 shows that the barriers are quite serious for women entrepreneurs because most of the women don't have permission to go out or use social media so that they can promote their business and results are neutral because few women have education and training to get marketing skills.

Table 03: Lack of management skills
LACK_MANAGEMENT_SKILLS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	3	9.7	9.7	9.7
Agree	11	35.5	35.5	45.2
Neutral	8	25.8	25.8	71.0
Disagree	7	22.6	22.6	93.5
Strongly Disagree	2	6.5	6.5	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 03 shows that they also faced problem in management skills because most of the women are talented along with, they have kids and households' stuff to do as well that is why they face problem in managing work life balance.

Table 04: Too Many Govt Regulations
GOVT_REGULATION

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
--	-----------	---------	---------------	--------------------

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

Valid Strongly Agree	4	12.9	12.9	12.9
Agree	9	29.0	29.0	41.9
Neutral	13	41.9	41.9	83.9
Disagree	5	16.1	16.1	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	0

Table 04 shows that majority selected the option neutral because in today's modern world most of the businesses are working online and that is easy for women who are house wives. Very small number of women chooses Agree because these are those who have business physically located in areas.

SECTION 03: SUCCESS

Table 01: Good General Management Skills

Good_Management_Skill

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Agree	5	16.1	16.1	16.1
Agree	20	64.5	64.5	80.6
Neutral	5	16.1	16.1	96.8
Strongly Disagree	1	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 02 of section 03 shows that majority of women selected Agree because management of the back bone of everything exists. Good management decreases the chances of risks or sudden problems.

Table 02: Previous business experience

Previous_business_experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	1	3.2	3.2	3.2
Agree	14	45.2	45.2	48.4
Neutral	13	41.9	41.9	90.3
Disagree	3	9.7	9.7	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 03 of section 03 shows that previous business experience affects the current business a lot because the mistakes entrepreneurs do in previous business will never repeated in the current business because they faced it earlier and they also know how to handle that particular situation.

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

Table 04: Good Product and Competitive Price

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	1	3.2	3.2	3.2
Agree	14	45.2	45.2	48.4
Neutral	13	41.9	41.9	90.3
Disagree	3	9.7	9.7	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 03 od section 03 shows that giving good quality product at competitive price will also impact good on their business because customers get the quality product at low price as compared to other business prices and the entrepreneurs herself get the maximum reliable customers

SECTION 04: FAMILY SUPPORT

Table 01: Work Family Conflict

Work_Family_Conflict

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	8	25.8	26.7	26.7
Agree	14	45.2	46.7	73.3
Neutral	5	16.1	16.7	90.0
Disagree	2	6.5	6.7	96.7
Strongly Disagree	1	3.2	3.3	100.0
Total System	30	96.8	100.0	
	1	3.2		
Total	31	100.0		

Table 01 of section 04 shows that the most of the women are house wives which are too talented and also want to grow their business globally but the factor family support can't make it happen because there is conflict between work and family.

Table 02: Family Support Is Very Important for Women Entrepreneurs

Family-support

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	22	71.0	71.0	71.0
Agree	8	25.8	25.8	96.8
Neutral	1	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	31	100.0	100.0	

Table 02 of section 04 shows that a majority has strongly agree to family support factors that shows if their families support them in their business, they can expand it widely and this is beneficial as well for the family and society and ultimately to the country.

4.2 Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: MOTIVATION

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.241 ^a	.058	-.012	3.02768

The model summary above demonstrates how the independent variable might influence the proportion of the dependent variable (i.e., entrepreneur Motivation). According to this Table, the R square value is .058 percent (i.e., .058), which means that the independent variable may account for .058 percent of the variation in the dependent variable, while the remainder can be explained by factors outside the scope of this model.

Dependent Variable:

Barriers/ Problems

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.503 ^a	.253	.198	2.36319

The above given model summary describes the percentage of the dependent variable (i.e., entrepreneurs' Barriers/ problems) that can be shown by the independent variable. In accordance of this Table, the value of the R square comes out to be .253% (i.e., .253), this infers that .253% of the difference in the dependent variable can be reported for the independent variable, while the remaining can be elucidated by other factors outside the scope of this model.

Dependent Variable: SUCCESS

Model Summary

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.152 ^a	.023	-.049	2.34649

5. CONCLUSION

This study discussed the cultural, social, economic/financial and contextual challenges that an emerging women entrepreneurs have to face during the start and growth of her business. Further highlight the different problems that must have overcome for the execution of business endeavours in Pakistan, we confirmed that the women entrepreneurs create the value for herself in the form of independent and financially sound position and for the society in the form of poverty alleviation and generate the employment opportunities for young graduates. She also acts as a role model for others, who are unemployed. They may serve themselves through taking the entrepreneurial initiatives.

Although women entrepreneurs need the support from her family members, who support her in managing the household work and provide her morally and financially support so that she will utilize her maximum potential for the exploitation of business opportunities otherwise she will be suffering mentally and physically by work life conflict women informants enforce on the human personal trait that will be the triggering factors to start-up entrepreneurship other than economic and contextual factors. If an entrepreneur has the quality of self-actualization, commitment and hardworking and also continuously keen to learn then she will exploit the business opportunities and can execute a successful business activity.

References

1. Abbasi, U. (2015). *Female entrepreneurship in Pakistan*. Retrieved from <http://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2015/11/25/comment/female-entrepreneurship-in-pakistan/>
2. Akehurst, G., Simarro, E., & Mas-Tur, A. (2012). Women entrepreneurship in small service firms: motivations, barriers and performance. *The Service Industries Journal*, 32(15), 2489-2505.
3. Alam, S. S., Jani, M. F. M., & Omar, N. A. (2011). An empirical study of success factors of women entrepreneurs in southern region in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 3(2), 166.
4. Al-Sadi, R., Belwal, R., & Al-Badi, R. (2011). Woman entrepreneurship in the Al-Batinah region of Oman: An identification of the barriers. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 12(3), 58.
5. Anjum, M., Khan, N., Raza, S. A., & Fatima, S. (2012). Problems and prospects of women entrepreneurs: a case study of Quetta-Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(23).
6. Bhardwaj, B. (2014). Impact of education and training on performance of women entrepreneurs: A study in emerging market context. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 6(1), 38-52.
7. Bordens, K. (2006). *Research Design & Methods*. New Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill.
8. Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2007). *Business Research Methods*. Oxford University Press.
9. Carter, N., Brush, C., Greene, P., Gatewood, E., & Hart, M. (2003). Women entrepreneurs who break through to equity financing: the influence of human, social and financial capital. *Venture Capital: an international journal of entrepreneurial finance*, 5(1), 1-28.
10. Constantinidis, C., Cornet, A., & Asandei, S. (2006). Financing of women-owned ventures: The

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

- impact of gender and other owner-and firm-related variables. *Venture Capital*, 8(02), 133-157.
11. Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. Sage publications.
 12. Dangi, N. (2014). Women Entrepreneurship and Growth and Performance of MSMEs in India. *International Journal*, 2(4).
 13. Ekpe, I., Mat, N. B., & Razak, R. C. (2010). The Effect of Microfinance Factors on Women Entrepreneurs' Performance in Nigeria: A Conceptual Framework. *International Journal of Business and social science*, 1(2).
 14. Goheer, N. A. (2003). *Women entrepreneurs in Pakistan*. International Labour Organization.
 15. Haq, A., & Safavian, M. (2013). *Are Pakistan's Women Entrepreneurs Being Served by the Microfinance Sector? Are They Being Served by the Microfinance Sector?* World Bank Publications.
 16. Hughes, K. D. (2006). Exploring motivation and success among Canadian women entrepreneurs. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 19(2), 107-120.
 17. Idrus, S., Pauzi, N. M., & Munir, Z. A. (2014). The effectiveness of training model for women entrepreneurship program. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 129, 82-89.
 18. Jamali, D. (2009). Constraints and opportunities facing women entrepreneurs in developing countries: A relational perspective. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 24(4), 232-251.
 19. Kaur, R., & Bawa, S. (1999). Psychological correlates of entrepreneurial performance among women. *Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 8(2), 195-205.
 20. Kirkwood, J. (2009). Spousal roles on motivations for entrepreneurship: A qualitative study in New Zealand. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 30(4), 372-385.
 21. Le, Q. V., & Raven, P. V. (2015). Woman entrepreneurship in rural Vietnam: success and motivational factors. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 49(2), 57-76.
 22. Leszczyński, D. (2013). The investigation into motivations, success factors and barriers among women small business owners: An overview of extant literature. *International Journal of Management and Economics*, 39(1), 108-125.
 23. Lockyer, J., & George, S. (2012). What women want: barriers to female entrepreneurship in the West Midlands. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 4(2), 179-195.
 24. Mack, N., Woodsong, C., MacQueen, K. M., Guest, G., & Namey, E. (2005). *Qualitative research methods: a data collector's field guide*.
 25. Mahmood, B., Khalid, S., Sohail, M., & Babak, I. (2012). Exploring the Motivation and Barriers in Way of Pakistani Female Entrepreneurs. *British Journal of Education, Society & Behavioural Science*, 2(4), 353-368.
 26. Makhijani, H. B., Kumbhar, M. I., Mughal, S., & Talpur, U. (2015). Women Entrepreneurship: Problems Faced by Rural Women Entrepreneurs in Sindh Province of Pakistan. *Journal of Basic & Applied Sciences*, 11, 274.
 27. Makweba, V. (2014). *The Impacts of Financial and Family Support in Motivating Women Entrepreneurs Tobecome Successful: THE CASE OF ILALA MUNICIPALITY (Degree of Masters of Science in Entrepreneurship)*. Mzumbe University.
 28. Ming-Yen, T. W., & Siong-Choy, C. (2007). Theorising a framework of factors influencing performance of women entrepreneurs in Malaysia. *Journal of Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability*, 3(2), 1.
 29. Niethammer, C., Saeed, T., Mohamed, S. S., & Charafi, Y. (2007). Women Entrepreneurs and Access to Finance in Pakistan. *Women's Policy Journal of Harvard*, 4.
 30. Noorinasab, A. R., & Azmoon, J. (2014). Status and Barriers of Women's Entrepreneurship in Iran: An Overview. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship & Business Environment Perspectives*, 3(1), 821.
 31. Orser, B. J., Riding, A. L., & Manley, K. (2006). Women entrepreneurs and financial capital.

Factors affecting motivations, obstacles, and performance of Women ...

- Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice, 30(5), 643-665.
32. Roomi, M. A., & Parrott, G. (2008). Barriers to development and progression of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 17(1), 59-72.
 33. Roomi, M., & Harrison, P. (2010). Behind the veil: women-only entrepreneurship training in Pakistan. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 2(2), 150-172.
 34. Roy, S., & Manna, S. (2014). Women in Entrepreneurship: Issues of Motivation and Choice of Business. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Management*, 3(2).
 35. Sadi, M. A., & Al-Ghazali, B. M. (2010). Doing business with impudence: A focus on women entrepreneurship in Saudi Arabia. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(1), 1-11.
 36. Saunders, M. N., Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2011). *Research methods for business students*, 5/e. Pearson Education India
 37. Tlaiss, H. (2013). Entrepreneurial motivations of women: Evidence from the United Arab Emirates. *International Small Business Journal*, 0266242613496662.
 38. Vadjal, J., & Vadjal, M. (2013). The role of husbands: Support or barrier to women's entrepreneurial start-ups?. *African Journal of Business Management*, 7(36), 3730.
 39. *WEF: Global Gender Gap Report 2015*. (2016). Retrieved from <http://reports.weforum.org/global-gender-gap-report-2015/economies/#economy=PAK>
 40. Weiss, N. A., & Weiss, C. A. (2012). *Introductory statistics*. Pearson Education.
 41. Welsh, D., Memili, E., & Kaciak, E. (2016). An empirical analysis of the impact of family moral support on Turkish women entrepreneurs. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 1(1). 3-12.
 42. Zhouqiaoqin, Z., Ying, X., Lu, Z., & Kumah, S. (2013). Factors that influence the success of women entrepreneur in China: a survey of women entrepreneurs in Beijing. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 18(3), 83-91.